

PEDAGOGICAL CONDITIONS FOR FORMING PROFESSIONAL AND PEDAGOGICAL COMPETENCE OF FUTURE PRIMARY CLASS TEACHERS

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Annotation: The article examines the concept of professional and pedagogical competence of a primary school teacher, considers the classification of professional competencies and skills of a primary school teacher, examines the elements of professional and pedagogical competence, defines the functions that a primary school teacher performs, identifies the stages of formation of the professional competence of a primary school teacher, and formulates pedagogical conditions for the formation of professional competence of a future primary school teacher.

Key words: primary school students, primary school teacher, pedagogical conditions, methodological and information competence.

Introduction. Recently, new terms have come into circulation in pedagogical vocabulary that are used to characterize the activities of an educator, namely, professional competence, professional competence, social competence, pedagogical professionalism and others [4, 5, 7]. Today, the concept of competence is becoming relevant [1]. Researchers associate this with many factors, since competencies are the indicators that make it possible to determine the readiness of a student or graduate for life, his further development and active participation in the life of society, and for a teacher - the formation of professionally significant personal qualities, that is, pedagogical professionalism [2, 3, 6].

Domestic pedagogy already has certain developments in the direction of the competency-based approach. The problem of competence at different levels of analysis has been developed by many scientists [8, 10].

Most scientists interpret the concept of competence differently. The most widespread definition in our scientific literature is the definition of competence as “a set of knowledge and skills necessary for effective professional activity, that is, the ability to analyze, anticipate the consequences of professional activity, and use information” [9, 11].

In the developments of scientists, in our opinion, the interpretations of B. Karimova deserve attention. Thus, in her studies, B. Karimova characterizes the content of a teacher’s professional competence with procedural and effective indicators and defines the professional competence of a specialist as the ability and willingness to perform personal professional activities [12, 13, 14].

B. Karimova considers the professional pedagogical competence of a teacher in the specialty and defines it as a set of skills of a teacher as a subject of pedagogical influence of a specially structured scientific and practical knowledge in order to best solve pedagogical problems [15, 18].

Having analyzed different definitions of the concept of “professional competence of a teacher,” we will try to give our own. The professional competence of a teacher is a set of versatile knowledge and practical skills that help to successfully carry out teaching activities, innate abilities to cooperate with other people, combined with appropriate moral qualities [16, 17].

Competence is defined as a personality property and is divided into several types (B. Karimova), on which a person’s maturity in professional activity is based [7, 9]:

- socio-psychological competence, which is defined as the ability of an individual to effectively interact with people around her in the system of interpersonal relationships (the ability to navigate social situations, choose adequate methods of communication);

- communicative competence - a conglomerate of knowledge, verbal and non-verbal skills and communication skills;

- professional and pedagogical competence as the ability for productive communication in the conditions determined by the pedagogical system.

The main elements of professional and pedagogical competence are:

1. Special and professional competence in the field of the taught discipline.
2. Methodological competence in the field of methods of developing knowledge, skills and abilities.
3. Social psychological competence in the field of communication processes.
4. Differential psychological competence in the field of motives, abilities, orientation.
5. Autopsychological competence in the field of advantages and disadvantages of one's activities and personality.

Directly included in the professional competence of a teacher are pedagogical activity, pedagogical communication, and the personality of the teacher as content blocks, which in turn are divided into:

- professional knowledge;
- pedagogical skills necessary for self-diagnosis and self-formation of this aspect of work;
- professional psychological positions;
- psychological qualities that ensure the implementation of this aspect of work, psychological new formations that arise during its implementation;
- psychological map of the state of work.

Thus, in general, the professional competence of a teacher is presented as a complex individual psychological education based on the integration of experience, theoretical knowledge, practical skills and significant personal qualities that determine readiness for the actual implementation of teaching activities.

As evidenced by pedagogical practice, future primary school teachers are prepared to perform the following functions [8]:

- managerial - act as a leader, that is, manage the educational and cognitive activities of students;
- managerial - to be an instructor helping students in identifying resources for completing educational tasks;
- controlling - act as an evaluator when it is necessary to monitor and evaluate the educational achievements of students;
- organizing - to be in the role of organizer of diverse activities of students;
- educational - act as a carrier of knowledge, be a guide on the path of students' education;
- diagnostic and prognostic - act as a researcher in determining the real degree of learning and development of students and predicting their educational trajectories on this basis.

That is why the key skills that a future teacher must have and which are indicated in modern educational qualification characteristics are:

- design the educational process, construct educational material, simulate pedagogical situations;
- transform scientific information into educational material;
- perceive the psychological state of students, determine the characteristics of relationships in the classroom;
- set correct tasks, coordinate the activities of schoolchildren, collaborate in the educational and cognitive process;
- produce bold, flexible thinking in search of the optimal choice of forms and methods of educational activities;
- master new scientific, pedagogical, scientific and technical knowledge, advanced, mainly non-traditional and non-standard methods of regulating relations with colleagues and parents of students;
- have an emotional impact on students;
- monitor the training, education and development of students;
- establish the degree of efficiency of its activities;

- creatively rethink the experience of practitioners.

The formation of professional competence is a cyclical process; in the process of teaching, a constant increase in professionalism is necessary, and each time the listed stages are repeated, but in a new quality. In general, the process of self-development is biologically determined and associated with the socialization and individualization of the individual, who consciously organizes his own life, and therefore his own development. The process of developing professional competence also strongly depends on the environment, so the environment itself should stimulate professional self-development. A democratic management system must be created at the school. This includes a system of incentives for employees, and various forms of pedagogical monitoring (not control!), which include surveys, testing, interviews, and intra-school events for the exchange of experience, competitions and presentation of one's own achievements.

We can distinguish the stages of formation of professional competence [1]:

- self-analysis and awareness of the need;
- planning of self-development (goals, objectives, solutions);
- self-identification, analysis, self-correction.

An important place in the formation of the professional competence of a future teacher is occupied by professional pedagogical communication, which is the main form of the pedagogical process. Professional pedagogical communication is a system of direct or indirect interactions of a teacher, implemented using verbal and non-verbal means for the purpose of mutual exchange of information and regulation of pedagogical relations. It ensures the transmission of human culture to students through the teacher, the assimilation of knowledge, and contributes to the formation of their value orientations. Pedagogical communication ensures the exchange of information, empathy, personal knowledge, and self-affirmation.

Speaking about the professional competence of a teacher, one cannot fail to mention the creation of his portfolio. A portfolio is a reflection of professional activity, in the process of formation of which self-assessment occurs and the need

for self-development is realized. Through a portfolio, the problem of teacher certification is solved, because here the results of professional activities are collected and summarized. Creating a portfolio is the motivational basis for a teacher's activities and the development of his professional competence.

So, learning to be a teacher means constantly thinking about how to scientifically rationalize the hard work of teaching, how to use all the possibilities of your subject, create a teaching methodology that will allow you to better teach and educate each student, while simultaneously creating conditions for the maximum development of his abilities and strength. Therefore, further research should be carried out in the direction of the teacher's active work on himself.

Conclusions. The prospects for further socio-psychological research into competence as a component of specialist training at a university lie in an in-depth study of learning motivation factors within the framework of the subject-subject model of organizing the educational process in modern education, aimed at the formation and development of a harmonious, highly competent personality of a creative professional. The problem of competence and its relationship with other scientific categories requires further theoretical understanding and exhaustive analysis.

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